

A primer on survival data analysis in presence of competing risks.

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Abstract

We recall the main conceptual definitions involved in the analysis of survival data in presence of competing risks and outline briefly the main descriptive and modelling approaches together with the most common associated pitfalls.

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Probabilistic tools

Probabilistic tools for a single event type

We denote by T the time elapsed until the occurrence of a certain event whose probability density function and cumulative distribution functions are denoted by f and F respectively. In classical statistical methods (most notably methods belonging to the generalized linear model family) the modeling focuses on the density f . In connexion with the fact that survival times are most often censored, survival analysis focuses on the hazard rate defined as

$$\alpha(t) \stackrel{def}{=} \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{\Delta t} p(T \in [t, t + \Delta t] | T \geq t)$$

For notational simplicity, we will often denote $p(T = t | T \geq t)$ (as well as other similar loopy notation) which should be understood as a density with respect to the proper probability measure.

The cumulative hazard rate is defined as

$$A(t) \stackrel{def}{=} \int_0^t \alpha(u) du$$

The functions f , F , α and A are related by the following equations:

$$\alpha(t) = \frac{f(t)}{S(t)} \tag{1}$$

$$S(t) = \exp -A(t) \tag{2}$$

$$F(t) = \int_0^t S(t)\alpha(t)dt \tag{3}$$

Probabilistic tools for survival data analysis in presence of competing risks

The data observed in the context of competing risks are typically a time to event T and type of event C . It is convenient to introduce T_k , the time to event of type k . If we study the life time of a mechanical or electrical device made of several components that will fail as soon as one of the component fails, the T_k are the life times of the various components which are perfectly defined and observable. In a context where the occurrence of an event precludes not only the observation of other events but also their occurrences (e.g. death precluding the occurrence of diseases), the T_k s can be thought of latent (i.e. non observed variables) conveniently introduced for the modeling sake.

The T_k s are related to the observed event time and type by $T = \min_k(T_k)$ and $C = \text{Argmin}_k(T_k)$.

In the context of competing risks, the T_k s are usually not observed jointly. In this setting, without an assumption of joint independance of the T_k s, the identification of their joint distribution is not possible (Tsiatis 1975).

We give below the definition of a few functional parameters useful to characterise the distribution of (T, C) .

All-cause survival function

$$S(t) \stackrel{def}{=} p(T \geq t) \quad (4)$$

Cause-specific hazard

The k -th cause-specific hazard is defined as

$$\alpha_k(t) \stackrel{def}{=} p(T = t, C = k | T \geq t)$$

Denoting by f_k and S_k respectively the pdf and survival function of latent time T_k , for independant latent failure times, we have:

$$S(t) = p(T \geq t) = p\left(\bigcap_k T_k \geq t\right) = \prod_k p(T_k \geq t) = \prod_k S_k(t) \quad (5)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_k(t) &= \frac{p(T = t, C = k)}{p(T \geq t)} \\ &= \frac{p(T_k = t, \bigcap_{l \neq k} T_l \geq t)}{p(\bigcap_l T_l \geq t)} \\ &= \frac{p(T_k = t) \prod_{l \neq k} p(T_l \geq t)}{\prod_k p(T_l \geq t)} \\ &= \frac{f_k(t)}{S_k(t)} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The k -th cause-specific hazard rate can be seen as the hazard of the k -th latent failure time under independance of the latent times. This relation also shows the hazard attached to event k is not affected by the distribution of other events times.

The k -th cumulative cause-specific hazard is defined as

$$A_k(t) \stackrel{def}{=} \int_0^t \alpha_k(u) du$$

Sub-distribution hazard

We define a random variable T' that is equal to T if $C = 1$ (assumed to be the event of interest) and to $+\infty$ otherwise. Then

$$p(T' \leq t) = p(T \leq t, C = 1) \quad (7)$$

The sub-distribution hazard is the hazard attached to T' :

$$\lambda(t) \stackrel{def}{=} p(T' = t | T' \geq t)$$

The sub-distribution hazard $\lambda(t)$ can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}
\lambda(t) &= \frac{p(T' = t)}{p(T' \geq t)} \\
&= \frac{p(T = t, C = 1)}{p(T \geq t) + p(T \leq t, C = 2)} \\
&= \frac{p(T \geq t)}{p(T \geq t)} \frac{p(T = t, C = 1)}{p(T \geq t) + p(T \leq t, C = 2)}
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Therefore, the cause specific hazard $\alpha_1(t)$ and the sub-distribution hazard $\lambda(t)$ are related through

$$\lambda(t) = \alpha_1(t) \frac{S(t)}{S(t) + p(T \leq t, C = 2)} \tag{9}$$

All-cause hazard

The all-cause hazard is defined as

$$\alpha(t) \stackrel{def}{=} \sum_k \alpha_k(t)$$

The cumulative all-cause hazard is defined as

$$A(t) \stackrel{def}{=} \sum_k A_k(t) = \exp - \int_0^t \sum_k \alpha_k(u) du \tag{10}$$

which relates to the all-cause survival function through

$$S(t) = \exp - A(t) \tag{11}$$

Incidences

The k -th cause-specific incidence is defined as

$$I_k(t) \stackrel{def}{=} p(T = t, C = k)$$

and satisfies

$$I_k(t) = S(t) \alpha_k(t) \tag{12}$$

The k -th cause-specific cumulative incidence is defined as

$$CI_k(t) \stackrel{def}{=} p(T \leq t, C = k)$$

and satisfies

$$CI_k(t) = \int_0^t I_k(u)du = \int_0^t S(u)\alpha_k(u)du \quad (13)$$

Remembering (cf. Eq. 11) that the all-cause survival functions $S(t)$ is a function of the various cause-specific hazards, Eq. 12 and 13 show that raw and cumulative cause-specific incidences depend on the various cause-specific hazards.

Note also that a naive estimation based on Kaplan-Meier treating the competing events as censoring will return an estimate of $\int_0^t S_k(u)\alpha_k(u)du$ where $S_k(t) = p(T_k > t)$ and is therefore biased.

A simulated example

We show now how the functional parameters introduced above can be used to describe the distribution of time to events. We illustrate the approaches with a simple simulated dataset where we assume the presence of two groups of 100 individuals each labelled A and B and two competing risks labelled 1 and 2. The hazard rates are assumed to be constant in time. For events of type 1, the hazard is assumed to be the same in group A and B , for events of type 2, they differ across the two groups.

```
## sample sizes
n_A = n_B = 100
n = n_A+n_B

## hazards
alpha_1_A = alpha_1_B = 1/100
alpha_2_A = 1/40
alpha_2_B = 1/120

## all-causes hazards
alpha_A = alpha_1_A + alpha_2_A
alpha_B = alpha_1_B + alpha_2_B

## time to event
T_A = rexp(rate=alpha_A,n=n_A)
T_B = rexp(rate=alpha_B,n=n_B)

## type of event
C_A = 2 - rbinom(n=n_A,size=1,p=alpha_1_A/alpha_A)
C_B = 2 - rbinom(n=n_B,size=1,p=alpha_1_B/alpha_B)

T = c(T_A,T_B)
C = c(C_A,C_B)
group = factor(c(rep('A',n_A),rep('B',n_B)))
dat = data.frame(T=T,C=C,group=group)
```

For a descriptive purpose, the most informative parameters are the cumulative cause-specific hazards and the cumulative cause-specific incidences. They are estimated by the Nelson-Aalen estimator and the Aalen-Johansen estimator respectively. This is done with `mvna` function of R package `mvna`.

```
library(mvna)
library(latex2exp)
mvna_dat = data.frame(id=1:n,from=rep(0,n),to=C,time=T,group=group)
tra = matrix(nr=3,nc=3,data=FALSE) ; colnames(tra) = rownames(tra) = 0:2
tra[1,] = c(FALSE,TRUE,TRUE)
tra # matrix specifying the possible transitions between states.

##      0      1      2
## 0 FALSE  TRUE  TRUE
## 1 FALSE  FALSE FALSE
## 2 FALSE  FALSE FALSE

res_mvna_A = mvna(mvna_dat[mvna_dat$group=='A',],
                 state.names=as.character(0:2),tra=tra,cens.name = 'cens')
res_mvna_B = mvna(mvna_dat[mvna_dat$group=='B',],
                 state.names=as.character(0:2),tra=tra,cens.name = 'cens')

par(mfrow=c(1,2),lwd=2)
plot(res_mvna_A$`0 1`$time,res_mvna_A$`0 1`$na,type='l',col='darkgoldenrod4',
     main='Event 1',xlab='time',ylab=TeX('$A_1(t)$'))
abline(a=0,b=alpha_1_A,col='darkgoldenrod4',lty=2)
lines(res_mvna_B$`0 1`$time,res_mvna_B$`0 1`$na,type='l',col='darkolivegreen4')
abline(a=0,b=alpha_1_B,col='darkolivegreen4',lty=2)

plot(res_mvna_A$`0 2`$time,res_mvna_A$`0 2`$na,type='l',col='darkgoldenrod4',
     main='Event 2',xlab='t',ylab=TeX('$A_2(t)$'))
abline(a=0,b=alpha_2_A,col='darkgoldenrod4',lty=2)
lines(res_mvna_B$`0 2`$time,res_mvna_B$`0 2`$na,type='l',col='darkolivegreen4')
abline(a=0,b=alpha_2_B,col='darkolivegreen4',lty=2)
```

The cumulative incidences are estimated with the `cuminc` function of R package `cmprsk`.

```
library(cmprsk)

## Loading required package: survival

res_cuminc = cuminc(ftime=mvna_dat$time,
                  fstatus=mvna_dat$to,
                  group=mvna_dat$group)

library(survival)
res_Surv_A = Surv(time=T_A,event=2-C_A,type='right')
res_survfit_A = survfit(res_Surv_A ~ 1)
```


Figure 1: Cumulative hazards. Continuous line: Nelson-Aalen estimator; dashed line: theoretical linear cumulative hazard.

```

par(mfrow=c(1,2),lwd=2)
tt= seq(0,200,l=1000)
plot(res_cuminc$`A 1`$time,res_cuminc$`A 1`$est,type='l',col='darkgoldenrod4',
      main='Event 1 ',
      xlab='t',ylab=TeX('$P(T \\leq t , C=1)$'),ylim=c(0,1))
lines(tt,(1-exp(-alpha_A*tt))*alpha_1_A/alpha_A,col='darkgoldenrod4',lty=2)
lines(res_cuminc$`B 1`$time,res_cuminc$`B 1`$est,type='l',col='darkolivegreen4')
lines(tt,(1-exp(-alpha_B*tt))*alpha_1_B/alpha_B,col='darkolivegreen4',lty=2)
## KM-based estimates
lines(res_survfit_A$time,
      1-res_survfit_A$surv,lty=1,col='grey')
lines(tt,1-exp(-alpha_1_A*tt),col='grey',lty=2)

plot(res_cuminc$`A 2`$time,res_cuminc$`A 2`$est,type='l',col='darkgoldenrod4',
      main='Event 2 ',
      xlab='t',ylab=TeX('$P(T =< t , C=2)$'),ylim=c(0,1))
lines(tt,(1-exp(-alpha_A*tt))*alpha_2_A/alpha_A,col='darkgoldenrod4',lty=2)
lines(res_cuminc$`B 2`$time,res_cuminc$`B 2`$est,type='l',col='darkolivegreen4')
lines(tt,(1-exp(-alpha_B*tt))*alpha_2_B/alpha_B,col='darkolivegreen4',lty=2)

```

Cox proportional hazard (CPH) models for competing risks

In a spirit similar to that of the model used in presence of a single type of events, the proportionnal hazard model can be used in presence of competing risks. We remind that this model posits that the log of a hazard rate can be written as the sum of function depending on time only (log- baseline hazard) and a linear combination of covariates.

The cause-specific proportional hazard model posits a CPH model for the various cause-specific hazards $\alpha_k(t)$:

$$\alpha_k(t) = \alpha_{0,k}(t) \exp(\beta_k X)$$

The sub-distribution hazard model posits a CPH model for the sub-distribution hazard of the event of interest:

$$\lambda(t) = \alpha(t) \exp(\beta X)$$

In the above, X is a vector of covariates and β_k and β are vectors of regression coefficients.

R resources

- The `cmprsk` package estimates the cause-specific cumulative incidence functions, performs a test of equality across groups and implements the Fine and Gray model (1999) for the subdistribution hazard.
- The `crrSC` package extends the `cmprsk` package to stratified and clustered data.

Figure 2: Cumulative incidences. Continuous line: Aalen-Johansen estimator; dashed line: theoretical cumulative incidences. In grey: estimates derived from Naive Kaplan-Meier estimation.

- The `crrstep` package implements stepwise covariate selection for the Fine and Gray model.
- The `kmi` package performs a Kaplan-Meier multiple imputation to recover missing potential censoring information from competing risks events, permitting to use standard right-censored methods to analyse cumulative incidence functions.
- The `pseudo` package computes pseudo observations for modelling competing risks based on the cumulative incidence functions. `timereg` does flexible regression modelling for competing risks data based on the on the inverse-probability-censoring-weights and direct binomial regression approach.
- The `riskRegression` package implements risk regression for competing risks data, along with other extensions of existing packages useful for survival analysis and competing risks data.
- The `Cprob` package estimates the conditional probability of a competing event, aka., the conditional cumulative incidence. It also implements a proportional-odds model using either the temporal process regression or the pseudo-value approaches.
- Packages `survival` (via `survfit`) and `prodlim` can also be used to estimate the cumulative incidence function.
- The `compeir` package estimates event-specific incidence rates, rate ratios, event-specific incidence proportions and cumulative incidence functions.
- The `NPMLEcmprsk` package implements the semi-parametric mixture model for competing risks data.
- The `MIICD` package implements Pan's (2000) multiple imputation approach to the Fine and Gray model for interval censored data.
- The `crskdiag` package provides graphical and analytical approaches for checking the assumptions of the Fine and Gray model.
- The `CFC` package permits to perform Bayesian, and non-Bayesian, cause-specific competing risks analysis for parametric and non-parametric survival functions.
- The `gcerisk` package provides some methods for competing risks data. Estimation, testing and regression modeling of subdistribution functions in the competing risks setting using quantile regressions can be had in `cmprskQR`.
- The `intccr` package permits to fit the Fine and Gray model as well other models that belong to the class of semiparametric generalized odds rate transformation models to interval-censored competing risks data.

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